

VOCABULARY TEACHING DIFFICULTIES OF SECONDARY ENGLISH TEACHERS

DOI

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Abstract:

Many secondary teachers face challenges in teaching English vocabulary in the classroom. Learning the different factors affecting the vocabulary teaching difficulties of the teachers could lead to possible solutions and interventions. This study aims to assess the level of difficulty of secondary English teaching in teaching vocabulary, particularly in the areas of content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, personal growth and professional development. A descriptive, qualitative research was conducted and used a 30-item survey questionnaire that passed the rigorous validity and reliability test. The assembled information was dealt with using the mean and Mann-Whitney U-tests. Results revealed that teachers had a low level of difficulty in the areas of content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, and personal growth and professional development. A difference was found in the teachers' level of difficulty in the areas of content knowledge and pedagogy and personal growth and professional development when compared according to highest educational attainment and plantilla position, and a difference was also found in the assessment area when compared according to highest educational attainment and length of service. The result provides evidence that teachers have less difficulty in vocabulary teaching; however, their vocabulary teaching difficulty varies based on the highest educational attainment, length of service, and plantilla position. This study calls for a continuous, high-quality training program in all regional secondary schools to address the vocabulary teaching difficulties of secondary English teachers.

Keywords: Vocabulary, Teaching Difficulties, Secondary English Teachers, Negros Oriental

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Samartin (2020) states that the English language is taught in basic education in the Philippines from third grade on up to grade twelve. In junior high school, English is one of the main topics where students begin to develop a deeper understanding of vocabulary and grammar to understand ideas through English. Hence, a teacher must be knowledgeable on content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, personal growth and professional development in vocabulary for teaching and learning.

In the present research venue, children with limited vocabulary skills may not have encountered a rich and rewarding culture of talk in their homes and communities or they may have limited access to reading resources through which new words may have been introduced (Sinatra et al., 2011). This gap is concerning because lack of vocabulary knowledge is more likely to result in great difficulty in expressing themselves both in speaking and writing. This is because teachers themselves need more ways to lessen difficulties in teaching vocabulary in content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, and personal growth and professional development. Hence, addressing difficulties in vocabulary teaching continues to be an essential challenge to educators.

Current State of Knowledge

English is a language that is spoken in so many different nations. Rumsey (2020) says that "English is spoken at a useful level by some 1.75 billion people worldwide". English is indeed a very significant language even online, with the majority of internet material being authored in this language. In parallel, DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 on Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers emphasizes that PPST shall be a basis for all learning and development programs for teachers to ensure that teachers are well-equipped to implement the K-12 program. The PPST domains collectively comprise of strands that refer to specific dimensions of teacher practices. One classroom situation that needs high focus is the teaching of vocabulary.

In a public secondary school, it has been observed that many teachers may not be aware how to apply their vocabulary knowledge and skills in various contexts as effectively as possible and may result to difficulties in teaching vocabulary. Some of the most basic principles of vocabulary teaching and learning have been forgotten or ignored (Alqahtani, 2015).

"In order for students to understand and enjoy the teaching -learning process in the classroom, teachers must be able to master the subject matter. In order to achieve the goal of language instruction, they must also create acceptable materials and effective teaching methods" (Elhamdi & Hezam, 2020, p.560).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study was anchored on Perkin's Theory of Difficulty by David Perkins (2007). The theory has been used widely by researchers in the field of education with various modifications as well as criticism. Teachers may not always respond appropriately to persistent problems in the classroom. One common response is to put the responsibility, and blame on the students, and continue teaching in the same manner. An even worse response would be to "teach harder," devoting more time and energy to addressing challenges without examining the reasons for their problematic teaching. Teaching requires much time and effort to make learning happen. According to Middendorf and Baer (2019) bottlenecks and threshold ideas concentrate on what makes a certain subject challenging. To put it another way, it identifies what kind of issue is preventing students in gaining knowledge. The tacit knowledge theory of difficulty aids educators in comprehending the reasons for problems. Normally, it is not surprising that learners make mistakes with some words they acquire and learn in the classroom. But sometimes mistakes come from the teachers themselves.

This theory's relation to the research, it is understood that Perkin's theory of difficulty is vital to the study because it has given new emphasis to many aspects of the vocabulary teaching process, especially for the teachers to understand their learners' weaknesses that trigger teaching difficulties. Teachers play an essential role in knowing the methodologies they need to utilize when teaching vocabulary. Hence, difficulties when teaching vocabulary should be identified first to know the strategies that must be applied in the teaching pedagogy. On the other hand, learners must take responsibility for vocabulary expansion.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching. More specifically, it aimed to determine 1) the level of teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, and personal growth and professional development; and 2) the significant difference in the level of teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching when grouped by age, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and plantilla position.

Methodology

Research Design

This paper used a descriptive research design to determine teachers' level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching. Descriptive research is a scientific method that involves describing individuals, events or conditions by studying them as they are and not trying to manipulate any of the variables. (Siedlecki, 2020).

Study Respondents

The participants were the 30 secondary public school English teachers in medium-sized District schools under Negros Oriental Division in Central Philippines. The researcher used purposive sampling, as all participants in the survey fit a particular profile for the study.

Instrument

This study employed a self-made questionnaire with 30 items on teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in the areas of content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, and personal growth and professional development. The survey questionnaire was presented to three (3) validators who are experts in the fields of education and research for further evaluation, comments, and suggestions. The validity index obtained a score of 4.89, interpreted as excellent, making the instrument valid. The reliability of the questionnaires was assessed through a dry-run test involving 30 teachers who were not part of the actual respondents to the study. The collected data was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha formula to determine the reliability rating. The computed alpha for this study was 0.793, interpreted as acceptable, indicating the research instrument is reliable.

Data Collection Procedure

Formal letters of permission were sent to the District Supervisors for their consent to allow data collection at the target participants. The same letters were sent to the school principals. When their notice of agreement returned, the researcher started to conduct the survey. Scheduled appointments were arranged for the actual survey and

retrieval to give enough time for the respondent to reflect and to ensure more accurate and quality information. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the participants was tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to process the encoded data in the computer.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching of secondary English teachers in content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, personal growth and professional development.

Objective No. 2 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-test to determine the significant difference in the level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching of secondary English teachers when grouped and compared according to profile variables.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure ethical considerations of research, all participants were informed about the details of the study. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the participants could withdraw without any consequences. They were informed about the academic purpose of the study. The researchers guaranteed the anonymity of the participants by assigning encrypted codes. Confidentiality was ensured as only the researcher had access to the research data.

Results and Discussions:

In this section, the data gathered were further treated, presented, analyzed, and interpreted to focus on the specific objectives of the study.

Table 1
Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I have difficulty...		
1. keeping a vocabulary notebook/note as my guide.	2.73	Moderate Level
2. explaining the definitions or contexts of words thoroughly.	1.67	Low Level
3. choosing which word to teach.	1.70	Low Level
4. finding the meaning of the newly introduced words.	1.43	Very Low Level
5. unlocking of difficult words.	1.27	Very Low Level
6. teaching vocabulary with sufficient knowledge and skills.	2.03	Low Level
7. with language in general.	1.90	Low Level
8. expressing my thoughts and ideas using spoken or written words.	1.73	Low Level
9. applying content to decipher unknown words.	2.23	Low Level
10. understanding root words.	1.17	Very Low Level
Overall Mean	1.79	Low Level

Table 1 presents the level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching of secondary English teachers in the area of content knowledge and pedagogy, with an overall mean of 1.79, interpreted as a low level. It shows that most secondary school teachers do not have radical difficulty in teaching vocabulary. On the other hand, the participants show difficulty in keeping a vocabulary notebook/notes as a guide, with a mean score of 2.73, interpreted as a moderate level. The difficulty in understanding root words was very low, with a mean score of 1.17. Most of the teachers were slightly struggling to keep vocabulary notes to serve as a guide in teaching. This is because most of the teachers do not have time to jot down important key points when teaching vocabulary. They always rely on the provided materials and resources available at hand. Hence, the majority of them did not exert effort anymore in keeping notes which was supposed to help them in tracking effective techniques in teaching vocabulary. The result aligns with that of Lukman (2021) wherein it was highlighted that in addition to the textbooks and chalkboards that are frequently available for use, it is generally important for school administrators and teachers to make sure that there are other resources that support or enhance their efforts in the teaching and learning process. Using notebooks for jotting down notes is one of the efforts teachers should master.

Table 2
Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Assessment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I have difficulty...		
1. constructing questions due to insufficient vocabulary.	1.13	Very Low Level
2. providing clear and unambiguous instruction due to lack of vocabulary.	1.23	Very Low Level
3. giving quiz to students after exposing them to word collocations.	1.70	Low Level

4. identifying the opposite word (antonyms) of some English words.	1.13	Very Low Level
5. applying lexical words.	1.87	Low Level
6. giving multiple spelling exercises.	1.67	Low Level
7. providing skit and dialogue that uses vocabulary words to act out in front of the class.	2.83	Moderate Level
8. providing activities involving vocabulary.	1.73	Low Level
9. providing activities using context clues.	2.13	Low Level
10. providing feedback due to insufficient vocabulary.	1.10	Very Low Level
Overall Mean	1.65	Low Level

Table 2 shows the level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching of secondary English teachers around assessment, with an overall mean of 1.65, interpreted as a low level. It shows that most secondary school teachers do not exhibit difficulty in teaching vocabulary in assessment. However, the participants show difficulty in the provision of skit and dialogue that uses vocabulary words to act out in front of the class, with a mean score of 2.83, interpreted as a moderate level. The level of difficulty in provision of feedback due to insufficient vocabulary was very low, with a mean score of 1.10. Sometimes teachers fail to provide skits and dialogue that use vocabulary words to act out in front of the class. The reason is that some of them have time constraints in making localized materials to be used by the learners as skits/dialogues. Also, teachers oftentimes do not access the use of online resources which is a great disadvantage in facilitating English classes because they stick to provided materials that do not suffice the needs and demands of the students. The result aligns with that of Zaidi et al (2017). The researchers found that the challenges faced by the teachers in role-play can be tough to conduct when the students are not familiar with the situation. Students must be able to identify other students' words, the context in which they are used, their mood, and their gestures. Hence, vocabulary plays a huge part in this kind of classroom performance. In the same vein, the study of Keezhatta (2020) found out that limited access to resources can also act as a challenge in the successful application of role-play as it requires access to resources including photocopies, access to computers and the internet.

Table 3

Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Personal Growth and Professional Development

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I have difficulty...		
1. continuing education.	1.80	Low Level
2. attending reading seminar workshops.	2.43	Low Level
3. developing strong communication skills.	1.93	Low Level
4. collaborating with my colleagues to enhance my vocabulary teaching methodologies.	2.77	Moderate Level
5. setting professional standards to uphold progressive teaching principles especially in teaching vocabulary.	2.63	Moderate Level
6. preparing and developing supplementary materials necessary for vocabulary teaching.	1.63	Low Level
7. Seeking advice from my experienced co-teachers to consolidate their best vocabulary teaching practices.	2.73	Moderate Level
8. engaging in collaborative learning along with my co-English teachers.	2.30	Low Level
9. displaying skills in planning and implementing vocabulary teaching strategies.	3.27	Moderate Level
10. seeking professional advancement and relevance in pursuit of vocabulary quality teaching.	3.10	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	2.46	Low Level

Table 3 depicts the level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching of secondary English teachers in the area of personal growth and professional development, with an overall mean of 2.46, interpreted as a low level. It shows that most of the secondary school teachers do not have extreme problems in engaging professionalism in teaching vocabulary. Meanwhile, the participants show difficulty in the display of skills in planning and implementing vocabulary teaching strategies, with a mean score of 3.27. The level of difficulty in preparation and development of supplementary materials necessary for vocabulary teaching was low, with a mean score of 1.63. Teachers have common problems in setting professional standards in vocabulary quality teaching. The reason is that most of the teachers have many responsibilities and workloads, hence, planning and implementing vocabulary teaching strategies were their least priority. They need enough time to prepare and craft effective techniques in teaching vocabulary. The finding aligns with that of Johal (2022). Her study revealed that if teachers are unable to complete tasks within their working day, the workload is inadvertently extended into the needed breaks provided by holidays. However, it is also marked that teaching and planning are understandably overwhelming at first. It is possible that with time and experience (within the classroom) teachers' time spent planning may be reduced. However, the finding contradicts the study conducted by Frake (2022), wherein she found that a vocabulary routine is a key and helpful way for teachers to plan and deliver instruction professionally. Vocabulary instruction

with quality requires teachers to prepare and plan the vocabulary words they will teach from the specific texts they are using in their classroom.

Table 4

Difference in the Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Content Knowledge and Pedagogy When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	15	15.07	106.00	0.806		Not Significant
	Older	15	15.93				
Civil Status	Single	10	15.05	95.50	0.846		Not Significant
	Married	20	15.73				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	22	19.09	9.00	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	8	5.63				
Length of Service	Shorter	15	17.00	90.00	0.367		Not Significant
	Longer	15	14.00				
Plantilla Position	Lower	12	20.33	50.00	0.013		Significant
	Higher	18	12.28				

Table 4 reveals the comparative analysis of teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching around content knowledge and pedagogy when compared according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and plantilla position. The computed p-values for age, civil status, and length of service are 0.806, 0.846, and 0.367, respectively, indicating no significant difference. However, the computed p-value for variables highest educational attainment and plantilla position are 0.000 and 0.013, which indicates a significant difference. The result implies that teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in content knowledge and pedagogy varies when compared according to highest educational attainment and plantilla position. The implication is that teachers with higher degrees in education and are in higher teacher positions commonly practice keeping separate notes related to vocabulary to help them with the smooth delivery of the lesson and classroom activity. The finding is opposed by Kerr (2016) who believes that whether someone uses a laptop or pen and paper, they must go back and check their notes as quickly as possible. The sooner they evaluate, the more adept they will be at recalling details that eluded their writing.

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Assessment When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	15	13.20	78.00	0.161		Not Significant
	Older	15	17.80				
Civil Status	Single	10	13.50	85.00	0.397		Not Significant
	Married	20	16.50				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	22	18.30	26.50	0.003	0.05	Significant
	Higher	8	7.81				
Length of Service	Shorter	15	12.37	65.50	0.050		Significant
	Longer	15	18.63				
Plantilla Position	Lower	12	16.88	91.50	0.491		Not Significant

Higher 18 14.58

Table 5 reflects the comparative analysis of teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in assessment when compared according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and plantilla position. The computed p-values for age, civil status, and Plantilla position are 0.161, 0.397, and 0.491, respectively, indicating no significant difference. However, the computed p-value for variables highest educational attainment and length of service are 0.003 and 0.050, which indicates a significant difference. This result entails that teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in assessment differs when compared according to highest educational attainment and length of service. The implication is that teachers of higher degrees in education believe that they have better way of assessing their learners' vocabulary compared to teachers who have lower degrees in education and consider themselves as being ahead of others concerning strategies in teaching vocabulary. The result of Mayani (2022) agrees with this feedback revealing that educators with high work maturity and experience display the knowledge, intelligence, and experience necessary to accomplish tasks independently. Their teaching abilities are enhanced over time which helps them face challenges and difficulties encountered in the teaching realm.

Table 6

Difference in the Level of Difficulty in Vocabulary Teaching of Secondary English Teachers According to Personal Growth and Professional Development When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	15	13.17	77.50	0.148		Not Significant
	Older	15	17.83				
Civil Status	Single	10	16.10	94.00	0.812		Not Significant
	Married	20	15.20				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	22	19.27	5.00	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Higher	8	5.13				
Length of Service	Shorter	15	14.93	104.00	0.744		Not Significant
	Longer	15	16.07				
Plantilla Position	Lower	12	19.63	58.50	0.035		Significant
	Higher	18	12.75				

Table 6 depicts the comparative analysis of teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in personal growth and professional development when compared according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, length of service, and plantilla position. The computed p-values for age, civil status, and length of service are 0.148, 0.812 and 0.744, respectively, indicating no significant difference. However, the computed p-values for highest educational attainment and Plantilla position are 0.000 and 0.035, which indicates a significant difference. The result entails that teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching in their personal growth and professional development varies when compared according to highest educational attainment and plantilla position. The implication is that teachers who have higher degrees in education and have higher ranks in teaching were mostly chosen to attend training and are likely to pursue professional advancement than their counterpart teachers. This disagrees with Mendoza's (2020) observation that new teachers require ongoing support in the form of professional development and advancement. Both are based on the ideas of lifelong learning and the agency's dedication to helping teachers reach their full potential in terms of practice improvement and student success. Teachers must be given equal chances and roles in the curriculum and professional advancement.

Conclusion:

In general, teachers' low level of difficulty in vocabulary teaching in content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment, and personal growth and professional development areas indicates a combination of proficient teachers, effective instructional strategies, well-developed resources, and a supportive educational environment. Keeping vocabulary notebook/notes as a guide, providing skit and dialogue that uses vocabulary words to act out in front of the class, and displaying skills in planning and implementing vocabulary teaching strategies are aspects that must be mastered also by teachers in the 21st century. These findings call for a continuous, high-quality training program in all secondary schools in the region to address teachers' difficulty in vocabulary teaching.

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